

Thermal behaviour of co-precipitated magnesium-aluminium hydroxides gel

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Abstract : Thermal behaviour of co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxides gel towards the formation of composite powders of periclase and MgAl₂O₄ spinel at low temperature was investigated. The co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxy compounds were synthesized at two different temperatures and at pH ranges in between 8.56 and 9.20 from chloride salts of respective ions with molar ratio for MgO : Al₂O₃ as 2 : 1 using various combinations of ammonium hydroxides, triethanol amine (TEA) and ammonium carbonate mixture as basic media for co-precipitation. The co-precipitated hydroxide gel dried at 110 °C and heated at different temperatures up to 1000 °C were characterised by DTA, TGA and XRD studies. In all cases the co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxy phases collapsed at 400 °C with the conversion to transient amorphous phases. Further heat treatment at higher temperatures led to the formation of MgAl₂O₄ spinel and minor periclase phases at temperature as low as 600 °C. The co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxides gel derived from TEA-NH₄OH basic media exhibited promising results so far as transformation to composite powders of MgAl₂O₄ spinel and periclase at relatively low temperature is concerned.

Keywords : Co-precipitation, basic media, Mg-Al hydroxide gel, MgAl₂O₄ spinel.

Introduction

The preparative methods of Mg-Al hydroxy compounds¹⁻⁸ is based on the interaction of various salts such as oxalates, chlorides and alkoxides of respective ions with different common basic media as precipitating agents viz. NH₄OH, NaOH and Na₂CO₃ etc. Thermal decomposition of derived Mg-Al hydroxy compounds provides a unique method for the preparation of MgAl₂O₄ spinel as co-precipitated precursors with homogeneous and fine particle dimensions are readily transformed into purified well defined spinel during heat treatment at comparatively lower temperature than that of traditional solid state sintering route using high purity magnesia and alumina as starting materials.

The pH of the basic media plays a very important role during co-precipitation process from a solution containing Al³⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions as Al³⁺ ion precipitates at pH from 4.0 to 7.5 while Mg²⁺ ions precipitates at pH 12.0⁷⁻¹¹, although both of them co-precipitate at intermediate pH values between 8.0 and 9.5. The complete precipitation of Mg²⁺ does not occur when NH₄OH is used as basic medium because of solubility of Mg(OH)₂

in NH₄Cl according to the following reaction¹² :

Again Al³⁺ ion forms soluble aluminates (AlO₂⁻) at higher pH when NaOH, Na₂CO₃ are used as basic precipitating agents. This is why the proper selection of basic media either singly or combination of bases for co-precipitation of microfine Mg-Al hydroxy compounds at intermediate pH values appear absolutely essential.

Gasmano *et al.*¹³ hypothesized a mechanism of MgAl₂O₄ spinel formation from the thermal decomposition of Mg-Al hydroxy compounds derived from NH₄OH as co-precipitating agent.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to study systematically the synthesis of co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxides gel in the molar ratio of MgO : Al₂O₃ as 2 : 1 during the interaction of different combination of basic media followed by in-depth study of the thermal behaviour of microfine co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxides gel of definite molar ratio in relation to variation of basic media and compounds formed in the gel precursor on heat treatment.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical characteristics :

The results of pH values during formation of the co-precipitated gels and the average particle size of the dried gel powders are presented in Table 1.

Sample code	pH during preparation of the co-precipitated gel	Average particle diameter micrometer (μm)
1MA	8.77	0.311
2MA	8.85	0.306
3MA	9.00	0.287
4MA	9.14	0.254
MAC1	8.74	0.326
MAC2	9.20	0.232
MAC3	8.56	0.315

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram for the preparation of co-precipitated gel.

NH_4OH -TEA basic media combination with increasing content of TEA exhibited continuously increasing pH

values as triethanol amine has stronger basicity than ammonia due to formation of HO^- ion according to the reaction :

The average particle diameter of the dried co-precipitated gel varied in the range between 0.232 μm and 0.326 μm in relation to different basic media. From the Table 1, it is evident that finest particle of co-precipitated gel was generated by basic medium containing NH_4OH -TEA in 1 : 1 ratio (v/v) and largest particle of co-precipitates by NH_4OH - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ basic medium respectively while other combinations of basic media produced co-precipitated gel with particle size lying in between the two values. Interestingly, an inverse relationship between average particle size of the co-precipitated gel and pH values of the reaction media during gel formation was observed.

Differential thermal and thermo-gravimetric analysis :

DTA and TGA curves of the synthesized co-precipitates were shown in the Figs. 2-5 respectively. Depending on varying experimental conditions such as precipi-

Fig. 2. DTA curves of the co-precipitates (1MA-4MA) prepared at room temperature ($30 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$).

Fig. 3. TGA curves of the co-precipitates (1MA-4MA) prepared at room temperature (30 ± 3 °C).

tating agents, temperatures and pH values during co-precipitation, there were differences in endothermic as well as exothermic peaks in the DTA curves of each of the seven gel-samples. Moreover the peak temperature and peak area of these endotherms were quite different from that of either aluminium hydroxide or magnesium hydroxide³. So it may be inferred that magnesium aluminium hydroxy compounds derived from different combination of basic media was not at all a mixture of individual hydroxide. In case of Mg-Al hydroxides co-precipitates (1MA to 4MA) obtained by varying proportions of ammonium hydroxide and triethanolamine as basic media, DTA curves showed a number of endothermic peaks. The initial endothermic peaks below 110 °C were due to removal of absorbed moisture that was physically bonded

Fig. 4. DTA curves of the co-precipitates (MAC1-MAC3) prepared in cold condition (12 ± 3 °C).

to the gel structure. The endothermic effect up to 280 °C was due to elimination of interlayer water. The minor variation as observed might be related to difference in particle size agglomeration nature and micro crystallinity of co-precipitates. XRD patterns of the dried co-precipitates (1MA to 4MA) showed mainly the presence of different forms of Mg-Al hydroxides viz. hydrotalcite [$Mg_6Al_2(OH)_{16}CO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$], indigirite [$MgAl_2(CO_3)_4(OH)_2 \cdot 15H_2O$] etc. The endothermic effects¹⁴ upto 500 °C may be explained by the dehydroxylation and the elimination of anions from the phases leading to collapse of layer structure and simultaneous formation of amorphous intermediate phases. Besides the major peaks, the presence of some small peaks in the DTA curves indicated heterogeneity in the hydrogel structure caused by the orientation of the water molecules. The exothermic peaks (2MA to 4MA) which were observed at 316, 329 and 548 °C may be attributed to the de-carboxylation of the hydroxy carbonate phases or the decomposition of organic compound such as triethanolamine adsorbed in the gel. TG curves (1MA to 4MA) showed (Fig. 3) that after the

Fig. 5. TGA curves of the co-precipitates (MAC1-MAC3) prepared in cold condition (12 ± 3 °C).

initial loss of adsorbed moisture at 110 °C, the thermal decomposition can be divided into three steps. Maximum dehydration was observed to occur up to 285 °C, weight loss become negligible at about 490 °C. Finally the weight loss almost ceased around 650 °C indicating formation of stable phases in the compound.

When the co-precipitations were carried out in cold condition (12 ± 3 °C), the low temperature peaks which were noticed for 1MA to 4MA samples, were not observed with (Fig. 4) MAC1-MAC3 samples derived from NH_4OH , $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-TEA}$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-(NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ as basic media respectively. This might be originated from the more compact nature of the co-precipitates in cold condition. In case of MAC1 where NH_4OH was used as basic medium, the dried gel powder exhibited the presence of Mg-Al-OH phase with poorly crystalline gibbsite. The first endothermic peak at 122 °C was due to elimination of water molecules from the interlayer space of the above mentioned phases. Peak areas of second and third

endotherms at 292 and 378 °C clearly indicated that maximum dehydration occurred around 292 °C and minimum dehydration around 378 °C. TG curve showed that after initial expulsion of interlayer water, maximum weight loss was noticed upto 360 °C (corresponding to DTA endothermic from 230–358 °C) and the weight loss became negligible at 500 °C (corresponding to DTA endothermic from 358–410 °C). Finally the weight loss was almost nil at 561 °C leading to the formation of stable phases.

In case of MAC2 based on $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-TEA}$ as basic medium the dried powder consisted of hydrotalcite [$\text{Mg}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{16}\text{CO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$] as major phase with minor content of magnesium aluminium hydroxide [$\text{MgAl}_2(\text{OH})_8$]. DTA curve showed two sharp endothermic peaks at 246 and 410 °C respectively indicating that dehydroxylation occurred in two stages. First stage was completed around 308 °C while second stage ended about 492 °C. Corresponding weight losses was also noticed in TG curve i.e. first stage was over at about 300 °C followed by a steep weight loss from 300 to 490 °C in the second stage of dehydration. Above 490 °C the weight loss was negligible and was more or less completed around 600 °C.

In case of MAC3 based on $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-(NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ as basic medium the dried powder contained only indigirite [$\text{MgAl}_2(\text{CO}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$]. DTA peak at 138 °C was attributed to the elimination of interlayer water and the peak at 359 °C was due to dehydroxylation of hydroxy carbonate phase. From the TG curve it has been noted that the weight loss upto 330 °C and upto 358 °C may be attributed to expulsion of interlayer water followed by the maximum weight loss upto 395 °C due to dehydroxylation of carbonate phase respectively after which weight loss was almost ceased at 500 °C indicating the completion of dehydration around that temperature with simultaneous formation of stable phases.

XRD analysis :

All the Mg-Al hydroxides co-precipitates dried at 110 °C and heat treated at 400, 600 and 1000 °C were sub-

jected to XRD analysis and XRD pattern of all the samples were shown in Figs. 6–9. In all cases formation of initial phases appeared very much influenced by the type of the basic medium and the temperature used during their

Fig. 6. XRD patterns of co-precipitates dried at 110 °C.

preparation. X-Ray analysis results of Mg-Al hydroxides heat treated at different temperature upto 1000 °C were discussed below.

110 °C (Fig. 6) :

1MA prepared at room temperature contained hydrotalcite $[Mg_6Al_2(OH)_{16}CO_3 \cdot 4H_2O]$ as a major phase with a minor gibbsite $[Al(OH)_3]$, whereas 2MA and 3MA prepared at room temperature, did not tally with any stan-

Fig. 7. XRD patterns of co-precipitates heat treated at 400 °C.

dard patterns but has some similarities with hydrotalcite $[Mg_6Al_2(OH)_{16}CO_3 \cdot 4H_2O]$, indigirite $[MgAl_2(CO_3)_4(OH)_2 \cdot 15H_2O]$ like compounds. Again 4MA based on aqueous TEA as basic medium contained only indigirite $[MgAl_2(CO_3)_4(OH)_2 \cdot 15H_2O]$ phase.

When the co-precipitations were carried out in cold condition (12 ± 3 °C) using different basic media, the nature of patterns altered significantly. Thus MAC1 obtained with aqueous NH_4OH , showed amorphous Mg-Al-OH phase with partly crystalline gibbsite $[Al(OH)_3]$. On the other hand MAC2 prepared by using NH_4OH -TEA as basic medium in cold condition exhibited in the presence of hydrotalcite as a major phase with a minor magnesium aluminium hydroxide $[MgAl_2(OH)_8]$. MAC3 prepared by NH_4OH - $(NH_4)_2CO_3$ as basic medium in cold condition, showed only indigirite phase. In most cases, formation of these hydroxy carbonate phases was due to substitution of hydroxyl ions of the interlayer sheet with carbonate ions, coming from atmosphere or from the basic medium as in MAC3 where $(NH_4)_2CO_3$ was incorporated in the basic medium.

Fig. 8. XRD patterns of co-precipitates heat treated at 600 °C.

400 °C (Fig 7) :

All the co-precipitates heat treated at 400 °C showed amorphous character to X-ray diffraction indicating that the crystalline structures of the initial compounds formed during co-precipitation was collapsed at that temperature. Bratton⁶ also reported that co-precipitated magnesium aluminium hydroxy compound on heat treatment between 350 and 400 °C yielded a product nearly amorphous to X-ray diffraction.

600 °C (Fig 8) :

When the co-precipitates were heat treated at 600 °C, $MgAl_2O_4$ spinel or spinel like phases had appeared in most cases. In some cases (2MA, 3MA and MAC1) minor periclase phase was also noticed. Maximum crystallinity was observed in 3MA and MAC2 samples where TEA was introduced for preparation of the basic medium.

Fig. 9. XRD patterns of co-precipitates heat treated at 1000 °C

1000 °C (Fig 9) :

At 1000 °C, well defined $MgAl_2O_4$ spinel peaks were noticed in all cases. 1MA-4MA samples exhibited also the presence of prominent γ -alumina phase and minor periclase phase at that temperature.

Experimental

Magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) and aluminium chloride hexahydrate ($AlCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$) (AnalaR grade BDH) were used as starting materials. Laboratory reagent grade NH_4OH (25%), $(NH_4)_2CO_3$ and triethanol amine ($CH_2OHCH_2)_3N$ were taken for preparation of basic media. Seven combinations of basic media with different

proportions of above bases in water were prepared for co-precipitation of Mg-Al hydroxy compounds as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Basic media combinations and end products during preparation of gel powders

Sample code	Basic media				End product
	NH ₄ OH (ml)	TEA (ml)	H ₂ O (ml)	(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃ (mole)	
1MA	80	10	10	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
2MA	60	20	20	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
3MA	40	30	30	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
4MA	-	50	50	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
MAC1	70	-	30	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
MAC2	40	40	20	-	Mg-Al hydroxide gel
MAC3	70	-	30	0.10	Mg-Al hydroxide gel

For synthesising mixed hydroxides hydrogel of magnesium and aluminium in the molar ratio of 2 : 1 at room temperature, requisite volume of respective salt solution containing 0.05 (M) Mg²⁺ and Al³⁺ were taken in a jar and each seven combinations of basic media was gradually added with vigorous stirring until gelation was complete. The pH of co-precipitated gel was measured for each of basic media used after completion of gel formation. The gel was then allowed to age for a period of 24 h followed by filtration, thorough washing with hot distilled water, drying at 110 °C and pulverisation. Some of the co-precipitation were also performed in cold conditions (12 ± 3 °C). The schematic representation for the preparation of co-precipitated gel with various basic media is shown in Fig. 1.

Average particle diameter of dried co-precipitates was measured by Malvern AUTO size-2C, UK instrument, using Laser beam. The thermal behaviour of all the co-precipitated gel were examined by differential thermal (DTA) and thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) using Shimadzu DT-30 and DT-50 (Japan) equipment respectively at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. For identification of crystalline phases in all dried and heat-treated samples at different temperatures up to 1000 °C, XRD analysis was employed using Philips diffractometer PW-1730 in-

strument, Holland. Ni filtered Cu-Kα, 40 KV and 20 mA radiations were used at a scanning rate of 2° min⁻¹.

Conclusion :

Thermal behaviour of co-precipitated Mg-Al hydroxides gel based on different basic media was summarized as follows :

(i) Type of basic media and temperature during co-precipitation played significant role on co-precipitation process from their salts solution as evidenced by the formation of different compounds.

(ii) Thermal analysis and XRD patterns showed that the co-precipitated powders were not the mixture of individual hydroxide.

(iii) Tri-ethanol amine or ammonium carbonate containing basic media favoured the formation of hydroxy carbonate phases.

(iv) All the co-precipitates on heat treatment at 400 °C exhibited amorphous character due to collapse of initial crystalline phases.

(v) Distinct differences in DTA curves were noticed due to variation of nature and extent of initial compounds formed during co-precipitation.

(vi) XRD patterns confirmed that spinel formation started at low temperature (600 °C) and best results were recorded with the co-precipitates (3MA and MAC2) respectively where tri-ethanol amine and ammonium hydroxide combinations were used as basic media.

(vii) XRD analysis also confirmed that heat treatment of most of the co-precipitates at 1000 °C profoundly generated well defined composite powders of periclase, MgAl₂O₄ spinel and γ-alumina phases.

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